

Human Resource Management: Implications of Quality-Oriented Teacher Recruitment for Improving the Quality of Education in Indonesia

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Abstract

Education has proven to be the basis of social equality and the advancement of independent and sustainable human resource development. The correlation between teacher quality and educational output has been well proven in the results of previous studies. This literature study aims to explore the potential use of resource management theory and practice in recruiting teachers who are oriented towards the quality and quality of education. The results of this study found that the needs of teachers in schools in Indonesia are different so that various recruitment management processes have been utilized, both by the central government, local governments, and school principals. The results of this study also provide a strong rationale for further research to demonstrate the great potential of harnessing expertise in quality-based teacher recruitment to lead to future improvements in the quality of education. The solutions to the obstacles faced in the recruitment process are the central government improves coordination and close cooperation with local governments to make teacher redistribution more evenly and ensure teacher recruitment is carried out following the needs at the education unit level; develop teacher performance standards based on measurable and comprehensive competencies and use these standards in developing teacher recruitment instruments, training programs, and performance evaluations. The findings of this study reinforce recent literature that identifies the teacher recruitment process as the basis for improving the quality of education.

Introduction

As a result of the political and security instability after the American occupation of the Iraqi lands in April Systems around the world strive to provide good quality education to their citizens, and this requires high-quality educators (teachers). Teachers have an important role in creating a quality learning atmosphere in (World Bank, 2019; Popova et al., 2016). According to Littlecott et al., (2018), the roles of teachers cannot be separated, but they support each other in carrying out their duties and functions based on their profession (Dahri Hussain et al., 2021)(Lorensius et al., 2021). They are also proactive about the need to develop and implement effective teaching practices. Therefore, the teacher recruitment system needs to be managed effectively, to ensure quality recruitment results. The problem of the low quality of teachers in Indonesia is still unresolved. The problem with teacher quality that we can see today is the high rate of teacher absenteeism in schools; lack of mastery of subject matter; lack of mastery of pedagogy; the general view of teachers that teaching and learning activities are the same as memorizing (Huang, 2020), and the teacher's lack of interest in innovating (Iskandar, 2018). According to Huang and Revina (2020) overcoming the problem of the low quality of teachers is a good way to improve the education system in Indonesia. That is, the nature of a teacher about education is to educate and at the same time teach following the knowledge he has.

The task and role of the teacher are to help students to be able to adapt to themselves, the environment, and society and be able to face various challenges of life. In Indonesia, policies issued to improve teacher performance are very diverse, ranging from increasing salaries, implementing certification programs, intensifying community participation in school management, developing pre-service teacher training, and connecting experienced educators with new ones for sustainable development (Huang & Revina, 2020). Quoting President Joko Widodo's speech (16 August 2019) that "Policies to improve the quality of Indonesian people will also emphasize improving the quality of teachers, starting from the screening process, teacher education, learning development, and appropriate teaching methods by utilizing technology." This means that the teacher recruitment process has a major impact on the quality and equity of education. Quality teachers are not only the main determinant of student achievement but also one of the determinants of evenly distributed educational resources (Darling-Hammond & Berry, 2016). Therefore, good management of human resources is needed to achieve school goals. As recommended by Alayoubi et al., (2020) that it is necessary to take into account

various strategic dimensions of HR development, strengthening organizational culture and emphasis on ethical practices and the application of balanced regulatory controls for educational services.

In Indonesia, teacher attendance rates in schools are considered poor (SMERU, 2015), low mastery of learning materials (Rosser & Fahmi, 2018; Kusumawardhani, 2017), limited pedagogical strategies for managing to learn in schools (Bjork, 2013), and lack of trust. teachers in developing problem-solving skills (OECD & ADB, 2015). One of the possible reasons why the quality of teachers in schools is still low is that teacher recruitment is based on short-term analysis, such as the number of teachers who leave or recruitment is only done in a certain year (Bloom, 2017; Worth et al., 2017) and recruitment what is done is not quality-oriented. The intuitive hypothesis may be to blame the employment recruitment agency, in this case, the relevant ministry. In Indonesia, there are two types of teacher status, namely as state civil servants and contract workers. State civil servant teachers are people who have passed the civil servant registration test. Meanwhile, teachers with the status of contract workers are those who are generally known as temporary workers or are employed informally. One of the objectives of the strategic plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture 2020-2024 is to expand access to quality education for students (Kemendikbud, 2020, p. 37). Meeting this goal will of course require qualified teachers, who are well versed with the teaching practices required to teach in schools. Literature facts show that teachers' teaching practices are closely related to teacher quality (Grossman et al., 2009). Based on the description above, this study aims to explore the potential use of human resource management theory and practice to identify and recruit teachers who are oriented towards the quality and quality of education.

Method

This study uses a qualitative approach with a literature study method. The research stages are carried out by collecting library data sources, classifying data based on research formulas, citing references to be presented as research findings, making abstractions to obtain complete information, interpreting data to produce knowledge for drawing conclusions (Darmalaksana, 2020). According to Zed (2004), library research is not only an initial step in preparing a research conceptual framework but also utilizes various library sources to understand new phenomena that occur. Through this literature study, the authors analyzes how the management of teacher recruitment in Indonesia is to obtain a recruitment strategy that is oriented to the quality or quality of education.

Results and Discussion

Teacher Recruitment Management

Empirical evidence and the results of previous literature reviews show that no professional development can compensate for inadequate employment recruitment practices. According to Mason & Schroeder (2010), weak policies on recruitment management and job security have an impact on staff turnover. Teacher turnover has been shown to damage student achievement, especially in low-performing schools. The negative effect of teacher turnover in schools is declining student learning outcomes, and it is often not matched by hiring new "better" teachers (Darling-Hammond, 2010). Based on this, teacher turnover certainly has a direct impact on student learning, school organization, and includes the non-collegiality of school organizational performance, not to mention the financial impact of recruiting and training new teachers. The recruitment and training of new teachers are significant financially. These costs drain resources that might otherwise be used to improve the school work environment, which is an important step in retaining qualified teachers. Therefore, policy measures to address teacher shortages are increasingly shifting towards teacher retention efforts (Ingersoll, 2019).

This study departs from empirical data from previous studies that support HR management practices and concerns in education regarding the recruitment of qualified teachers as human resources in the school context. Human resource management research by Heneman et al., (2009) suggests person-job fit to resolve specific job requirements and the determination of the applicant's skills, attitudes and motivations. Organizations are also advised to look for personal organization fit which is an alignment between the applicant's values and the values in the organization (Heneman et al., 2009). According to Ng and Sarris (2012), the person-organization fit will be more likely to ensure organizational support, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. The most important school quality improvement strategies are improving teacher quality, teacher recruitment quality, and human resource management in educational institutions. Decisions regarding hiring and placement should stem from current staffing levels and projected reductions, but many countries have difficulty maintaining accurate teacher numbers including Indonesia, and are struggling with system capacity issues, poor data collection and entry, and lack of technical support (Custer et al., 2018). Peterson (2002) suggests that there are three steps in the recruitment process, each step involving improving the quality of knowledge. The first step focuses on screening paper credentials, which are low-cost processes and produce relatively shallow information and serve to reduce the pool of candidates to a manageable number. The second step, analyzing a more in-depth document, usually the second step is a medium-cost process that collects much higher quality information. The third step, consisting of selection and recruitment. Given that the information obtained at the second level of this

process is the basis of most recruitment, it is important to consider the elements that are given the most weight and are considered the most important in the recruitment process.

UN member countries have agreed on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which contain various development goals, one of which is expected to be achieved by 2030, namely the quality of education that is sustainable in (Schwan, 2019; Commonwealth Secretariat, 2017). The Indonesian government continues to strive to improve the quality of the education sector. One of the efforts made is the recruitment of educators (teachers) related to the country's development needs. The focus on Indonesia's economic development encourages further efforts to improve the teacher recruitment process. The strategic plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture 2020-2024 states that in order to strengthen the implementation of education development programs, it is carried out through coordination of relevant agencies to determine the formation and recruitment of teachers based on academic performance and quality (Kemendikbud, 2020, p. 55). Referring to government policies regulated in Government Regulation Number 11 of 2017 concerning the management of state civil servants, the procurement process starts from planning for employee needs, announcements, registration, administrative selection, selection of basic competencies, selection of field competencies, and determination of graduation, proposals determination of employee identification numbers, issuance of rank decrees as candidates for state civil servants, up to appointments as state civil servants.

Prospective teachers must take the state civil apparatus registration test to become an employee. The test is developed by the central government and administered by the provincial or local government. The pre-2013 paper-based civil servant candidate test was conducted by the district or provincial government, which was judged to have a risk of corruption because the candidate could bribe local government bureaucrats to pass the test. In 2013, the central government implemented a computer-assisted test (CAT) system to replace paper-based tests. Then, the results of the registration test are reported to the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform, but civil servants who are accepted by the test are employed under the management jurisdiction of the provincial or district government. As a result, teachers in Indonesia have to go through a highly centralized recruitment process. Prospective teachers must pass the selection of candidates for state civil servants before being assigned to certain schools. While this was made for efficient recruitment as decision-making regarding employment was centralized and prevented corruption at the periphery, teachers were not recruited effectively. The provinces in Indonesia are diverse and the centralized recruitment system does not take into account local preferences and needs. In fact, the administrative criteria and basic competency tests for state civil servants are the same for all professions nationally. For example, applicants for state civil servants who occupy the positions of teachers and hospital nurses, will take the same basic competency tests, namely citizenship, psychological tests, and general intelligence with identical passing scores. For each test round, the top three candidates with the highest scores will be selected for the next round. Selected candidates then need to take a field-specific test to qualify for their desired position. Thus, the top three teacher candidates will be asked to take a pedagogical and material knowledge test. Micro-teaching or interviews are not required in this teacher recruitment process. The candidate with the highest score in the special field test will be appointed as a teacher candidate for the state civil apparatus on a probationary period up to appointment as a state civil servant.

As teacher shortages persist in many regions, provincial and district governments follow regulations by letting schools recruit their own teachers, mostly on a contract basis. In contrast to state civil servant teachers who have to take a series of tests to get a job, contract teachers are recruited informally by school principals (Lorensius et al., 2021; Anggal et al., 2019). Contract teachers are paid from the school budget. School operational assistance funds are received by schools directly from the central government. Al-Samarrai and Cerdan-Infantes (2013) estimate that 260,000 contract teachers were paid by the school operational assistance fund from 2006 to 2010. Contract teachers typically earn very little salaries (Chudgar et al., 2014). Gaduh et al., (2020) note that a teacher in the state civil service can receive a salary fifteen times higher than the salary of a contract teacher. Note that civil servants and contract teachers have almost the same responsibilities. Contract teachers bear the burden of working with such low salaries, because they hope that one day they can be appointed as civil servants without having to take the test for candidates for state civil servants. Following the enactment of Government Regulation No. 48 of 2005 concerning the Appointment of Honorary Personnel as probationary state civil servants, many contract teachers under the age of 46 years (above the age requirement of general state civil servant applicants) are automatically promoted to civil servants as a special exception to the application of the regulation. The 2005 regulations set a precedent. Contract teachers are still demanding to be automatically promoted to state civil servants to this day.

Since 2010, contract teachers have been gradually promoted to civil servants. Since promotion to civil servants has become the central government's approach to teacher recruitment, the teaching profession has become more attractive. Especially when the teacher certification allowance which doubled the teacher's salary was implemented in 2007 (Kusumawardhani, 2017). As teacher management in Indonesia is divided between local (provincial and district) and central governments, teacher distribution channels are ad hoc and localized to the district level. Schools in remote areas typically have higher student-teacher ratios than schools in urban areas, indicating a preference for urban areas due to their spatial proximity to urban centers as well as their

density with positions of power (Chang et al., 2014). However, regulatory changes to teaching incentives and management have widened the gap in institutional responsibility for the recruitment and management of educators. Contract teachers and state civil service teachers have dual responsibilities to both local schools and the central ministry that oversees the education system and civil servants. As a result of this reform, the issue of the effectiveness of the recruitment of educators and personnel must be examined by the political and social dynamics of the profession.

Difficult factors in recruiting quality teachers

The following will describe the institutional dimensions, political economy, and social elements as obstacles in the teacher recruitment process in Indonesia (Huang & Revina, 2020). The teacher recruitment system can be said to be not quality-oriented according to needs. The recruitment of state civil servant teachers and honorary staff seen from the recruitment process and tenure is not quality oriented. Teachers of the state civil apparatus follow the schedule and mechanism for the acceptance of candidates for the national state civil apparatus and the probationary period for the state civil apparatus is only a formality. Meanwhile, there is no special standardization for honorary teachers, and most are recruited by school principals. Teachers with honorary status also have no certainty of employment status and tenure (figure 1).

Figure 1. Teacher recruitment process in Indonesia (Huang & Revina, 2020)

The teacher recruitment process did not go well due to political and legal problems. The teaching profession is regulated in laws and regulations that obscure rather than clarify institutional responsibilities for the recruitment process. The division of authority for teacher recruitment between ministries as well as between the central government and local governments is still overlapping (figure 2).

Figure 2. Overlapping of Authorities (Huang & Revina, 2020)

Furthermore, the existence of political economic interests from various parties is one of the weaknesses of the teacher recruitment system. As there is a reluctance to go towards an effective recruitment system, for example, in the past there were often cases of entrusting teachers to the state civil apparatus. Then, honorary teachers who are accepted at schools are usually relatives or acquaintances of teachers and school principals, with the promise of appointment as teachers of the state civil apparatus and even honorary teachers are often used as political commodities from various parties, especially when elections are approaching. In terms of social dynamics, with various advantages in terms of income received by state civil servant teachers, the main goal of becoming a teacher is to obtain state civil servant status. In addition, because teachers are part of the government apparatus, the priority at the time of selection is national insight and general knowledge rather than teaching skills. Even from prospective teachers there are those who think that it is not necessary to be smart to be a teacher, they can start as honorary teachers and later will be appointed as state civil servants. From the description above, it can be concluded that there is no commitment from various parties to improve the quality of teachers. The factors that make it difficult to recruit qualified teachers in Indonesia are institutional factors, political economy, and social dynamics.

Conclusion

Several studies have explored teacher recruitment management. Recruiting qualified teachers is very important to ensure the quality of education in the future. The results of this study have implications for a comprehensive set of policies to address the problem of teacher recruitment and to ensure teacher commitment to the profession. Therefore, the policy on teacher recruitment is the first step to develop quality and competent teaching to achieve quality education. In addition, policies also need to eliminate inhibiting factors in the

recruitment process to maintain the clarity and prestige of the teaching profession. Human resource management that focuses on improving teacher competence is the goal of recruitment. The competencies in question include pedagogic, personal, social, and professional competencies. With the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which are challenges as well as opportunities globally, human resource management through an effective teacher recruitment process will encourage quality education and be globally competitive as well.

Recommendations

The solutions to the obstacles faced in the recruitment process are: (a) the central government improves coordination and close cooperation with local governments to make teacher redistribution more evenly and ensure teacher recruitment is carried out following the needs at the education unit level; (b) develop teacher performance standards based on measurable and comprehensive competencies and use these standards in developing teacher recruitment instruments, training programs, and performance evaluations.

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